

USAGE OF INFORMATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING SOFTSKILLS

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Abstract. *Digital technologies create new opportunities for the formation of intellectual capital and the development of the digital economy. Information technologies create favorable opportunities for the application of non-cognitive competencies, so-called "soft skills". Their mastering depends on both the conditions of digitalization of the environment and the activity of specialists themselves. At the same time, little is known about the preferences in the choice of technologies and means of digitalization of specialists for the development of softskills in the conditions of professional training and retraining. In this article, the authors experimentally investigate the composition of soft skills and preferences in the choice of digital tools and technologies among students and young specialists who are part of the personnel reserve of a large defense-industrial enterprise.*

Keywords: *intellectual capital, soft skills, digital tools and technologies, development, student youth, young professionals, motivation for self-development.*

Annotatsiya. *Raqamli texnologiyalar intellektual kapitalni shakllantirish va raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish uchun yangi imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda. Axborot texnologiyalari "yumshoq ko'nikmalar" deb ataladigan kognitiv bo'lmagan kompetentsiyalarni qo'llash uchun qulay imkoniyatlar yaratadi. Ularni o'zlashtirish atrof-muhitni raqamlashtirish shartlariga ham, mutaxassislarning o'z faoliyatiga ham bog'liq. Shu bilan birga, kasbiy tayyorgarlik va qayta tayyorlash sharoitida softskilllarni rivojlantirish uchun mutaxassislarni raqamlashtirish texnologiyalari va vositalarini tanlashda imtiyozlar haqida kam narsa ma'lum. Ushbu maqolada mualliflar yirik mudofaa-sanoat korxonasining kadrlar zaxirasiga kiruvchi talabalar va yosh mutaxassislar o'rtasida raqamli vositalar va texnologiyalarni tanlashda yumshoq ko'nikmalar va imtiyozlarning tarkibini eksperimental ravishda o'rganadilar.*

Kalit so'zlar: *intellektual kapital, yumshoq ko'nikmalar, raqamli vositalar va texnologiyalar, rivojlanish, talaba yoshlar, yosh mutaxassislar, o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish uchun motivatsiya.*

The intensive development of digital technologies and their widespread penetration into all spheres of life set new challenges for the system of vocational education to create a flexible digital environment for training and retraining. The formation of the most important resource of the digital economy - intellectual capital - creates a scientific foundation for its development. Over the last 20 years, the human being himself and the conditions of the labor market have changed dramatically.

The knowledge of the dynamically changing modern labor market and labor conditions in the conditions of digitalization requires the same close attention. The habitual understanding of the labor market with established professions and regional boundaries is a thing of the past, while

its diversification and the emergence of new professions, new tasks and functions are being introduced, and the related nature of labor is intensifying. Therefore, the knowledge about the possibilities of young people in training to adapt to the developing labor market and their awareness of the changing requirements for specialists is of particular importance.[1]

It is known that information technology is displacing humans from all spheres, types and operations of activity where work can be performed by a robot. Digital technologies have a strong impact on the transformation of labor relations and organization of work in companies. As M. Ford states “Generally speaking, no one will do anything that involves routine and repetition anymore”. The author emphasizes that “computers are better and better able to perform highly specialized, routine and predictable tasks and, quite probably, will soon surpass in this skill many people now engaged in such work” [9]. That said, in addition to the growing need for digital skills, the evolving digital economy is creating particularly favorable opportunities for non-cognitive, “soft skills” that computers cannot perform and are therefore in demand. These typically include social, emotional and behavioral skills and available research in developed countries shows that wages are higher for those who are good at soft skills [8].

The actualization of this problem is due to the fact that the requirements for a new quality of workforce in the labor market associated with digitalization obliges all countries to adjust their education and training systems to develop the skills required by the digital economy. Such studies are emerging, but they are not systematic. According to D. Newman, the acuteness of the problem is underscored by the fact that digital technologies and learning models personalize learning and require constant IT support. The use of artificial intelligence for educational purposes has made it possible to create an online advisor for students, available 24 hours a day, and thus offer previously unimaginable opportunities for students, making virtual excursions, not just reading text [6]. The optimal use of available digital technologies requires special environmental conditions and motivation for self-development of students themselves, the research of which is practically not presented.[2]

There is no research in the literature on the preference for the selection of soft skills or soft skills, which are independent of the specifics of the job and relate to personal development. Soft Skills (hereinafter - SS) are understood as a set of non-specialized, career-important professional skills that are responsible for successful participation in the work process, high performance and are cross-cutting, i.e. not related to a specific subject area. Flexible skills, unlike professional skills in the traditional sense, are not job-specific, are closely related to personal qualities and attitudes (responsibility, discipline, self-management), as well as social skills (communication, particularly listening; teamwork, emotional intelligence) and managerial skills (time management, leadership, problem solving, critical thinking).

Digital technologies are changing the information and technological space of education, which extends far beyond the boundaries of educational organizations and the competence of educational authorities. The question of new educational strategies is actualized, for which all participants of education should be ready, and innovative environmental conditions should be created to test the technologies for the implementation of these strategies [4]. Massive open online courses are considered as a realizable strategy on a global scale [9].

Available studies on methods and tools of digitalization of education, in our opinion, can be divided into professional (related to the direction of training or professional field) and universal (general, important for self-education in any field). According to Kochetkova O.V. and Kochetkov A.B., the universal program-pedagogical means of interest to us in the training of bachelors in the direction of “Economics” should include the following: electronic textbooks, should include the

following: electronic textbooks; computer training programs; computer learning environments (worlds); authoring tool environments; office software (table processor and database management systems), as well as for structuring and replication of knowledge in different subject areas - ontology editors: Apollo, CoGITaNT, Contextia, DAMLImp (API) [3].

As a related study of foreign authors on a set of facts about the use and acceptance of digital technologies in the context of blended learning, we highlight the 2018 work of a group of authors, which continues the pool of research using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) [9]. The results of the study, drawn from a sample of students enrolled in different undergraduate programs in resource-limited higher education institutions in Africa, confirmed the importance of four interdependent components for the acceptance and use of digital technologies: student access to digital technologies, student awareness of their use, student ability to use them, and lecturer characteristics. The digital technologies recommended by the authors for student use in resource-limited HEIs according to the results of the study should include: cloud-based service tools for personalized learning, cell phones to enhance collaboration between students and lecturers allowing instant communication, audio and video downloads, flexibility related to storage and playback of saved files, etc. These findings support previous studies, including those at Makerere University [9] cited by the authors.

One of the strategies implemented in different countries is the concept of Smart Universities, which implies an interactive educational environment, flexibility and personalization of education along with free access to the necessary content. "Smart education (smart learning) is an association of educational institutions and faculty for joint educational activities on the Internet on the basis of common standards, agreements, technologies and a single repository of educational materials" [5, c. 2-7]. At the same time, there are studies that emphasize not only the advantages of mass open online courses for higher education, but also the problems that have arisen. They are related to the fact that the realities of such courses may differ from the planned results, there is a high dropout rate, low motivation of students due to the fact that basic knowledge is required, there are violations of teaching and learning methods [8].

All related studies on digital technologies and tools are usually related to the formation of basic professional competencies. There are no studies on the selection and application of digital technologies in the formation of soft competencies. At the same time, as related studies of SS themselves can be noted a great number, summarized also in our work: the study of the list, choice preferences, model of social and personal competencies, including comparative cross-country studies. Our historical and genetic analysis of the main concepts describing personal, socio-cultural or universal competences in the model of a specialist of a new socio-cultural type [6, p. 59] shows that the foundations of their purposeful development were laid by the Bologna Declaration and the subsequent Bologna process, aimed at creating a common educational space that expands the mobility of students in higher education institutions of the European continent. For a long period of time we have been conducting research on Soft skills as socio-personal or universal competencies, the importance of which for professional development has been confirmed by students of different universities of SCO countries, teachers, employers [8].

Thus, it is necessary to accumulate material on the selection and application of digital technologies in the formation of SS taking into account the motivation, awareness and capabilities of students and young professionals, who constitute the intellectual capital of society and have a direct impact on labor relations in the digital economy.

As we have noted, all related studies on digital technologies and tools tend to refer to the formation of basic professional competencies in students. This study opens new horizons for us to

accumulate material on the selection and application of digital technologies in the formation of soft competencies. This will allow to concretize the opportunities for the young people to adapt to the developing labor market and their awareness of the changing requirements for specialists, and the management of educational institutions to constantly maintain a real dialogue between the university and the employer and “complete” the requirements for the training of a graduate on the requirements for SS.

Under the influence of key innovative practices related to the use of digital technologies, young people are forming a different way of life, not just contributing to the rapid completion of socio-cultural modernization processes in them, but also corresponding to the information economy, allowing them to successfully fit into the new conditions. But the requirements for a new quality of workforce in the labor market, associated with digitalization, obliges the university to adjust its education and training systems to develop the skills required by the digital economy, which requires managerial decisions and appropriate training of lecturers. Due to the unprecedented growth of the Internet and the subsequent transformation of educational technologies, it is necessary to understand how users perceive and use digital technologies to shape and develop Soft Skills.

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